

Open Government Data for Citizen Participation: Where is the Added-value?

Supplementary material

Appendix 1 – Interview Guide

In preparation for the interview, the interviewees are asked to fill in a document with the short name, description, and status (i.e., past, present, future, possible) of 3 citizen participation projects in which OGD has no or little added-value, 3 in which OGD has moderate added-value, and 3 in which OGD has high added-value.

Step 1 - Introduction and consent. During this interview, we would like to find out about your views of how open data can bring added-value to a citizen participation project. There are no right or wrong answers, we are precisely seeking to understand your opinions. This research is conducted anonymously, and the interviews will be analyzed in an aggregated manner. With your consent, we would like to record the interview. The recording will be securely stored and deleted upon completion of our research. Only our research team will have access to this material. Before we move on, do you consent to the recording of the interview, and do you have any questions about the interview process or our project in general?

Answer questions and proceed with the interview if terms are agreed.

Step 2 - Interviewee introduction. Before we get to discussing the list of citizen participation projects you kindly prepared, we would like to ask you to introduce yourself in a few words? What is your role in the municipality? What are your main tasks?

Step 3 - Elements elicitation. In this interview, we would like to reflect with you on citizen participation projects that you listed for us in preparation for the interview. If you have listed less than 9 projects, are there any projects you would like to add now?

Complete the list with projects added by the interviewees.

If there are still less than 9 projects in total, we would like you to look at this list of 12 project examples that are documented in scientific literature. These projects involve citizen participation and open data. Please select as many projects as you need to arrive at a list of 3 in which OGD has no or little added-value, 3 in which OGD has moderate added-value, and 3 in which OGD has high added-value. When choosing these projects and discussing them during the rest of the interview, imagine that they were implemented or planned in your municipality.

Complete the list with examples from the literature.

Step 4 - Warm-up. We will do a comparison exercise in which we will ask you to tell us how some of the projects are similar or differ. We will work with sets of three projects and ask you how two of them are similar, but different from the third one. We will repeat this process a few times.

Before heading into it, we would like to give you a short warm-up to clarify how this exercise will unfold. We will ask you to find contrasts when comparing the sets of three projects. A contrast represents one way of how you see projects as similar or different. It could be a scale, a pair of opposites, a pair of a synonym and an antonym, a pair of a positive and a negative. But if it is a contrast to you, it is good for us. To give you an example, imagine someone comparing three managers in terms of how effective they are at handling people. They could find that (a) 2 managers have a good sense of humor while the third takes everything seriously. Or that (b) 2 managers are too dogmatic while the third is a good listener. Or that (c) 2 managers have a positive commitment to day-to-day situations while the third shows little interest in day-to-day matters.

This is the type of comparisons we will ask you to make, but with citizen participation projects, and keeping in mind the context of the added-value brought by OGD. Let us now do a quick training exercise. Consider a nail, tape, and a screw. How are two of them similar but different from the third when it comes to securing something to a wall?

Perform the training exercise and proceed.

Step 5 - Guideline and clarifications. We will now move to the comparison exercise. We will work with sets of three projects and ask you how two of them are similar, but different from the third one. We will repeat this process a few times. Are you ready to start?

Answer questions and proceed.

Step 6 - Construct elicitation. Let us take projects X, Y, and Z. Keeping in mind our OGD context, which two do you view as the most similar and how do they differ from the third one?

If one pole of the construct C is unclear, use laddering with prompts such as

- *How is a project that is [pole of construct C] different from others?*
- *Can you explain what you mean by [pole of construct C]?*
- *Why is [pole of construct C] important to you?*
- *In what way [pole of construct C] differs from the opposite term you used?*

Step 7 - Rating of triad. Please rate the three projects on a scale of 1 to 7, 1 being closest to the characteristic written on the left and 7 closest to the characteristic on the right.

Step 8 - Rating of all elements. Now, please rate the remaining 6 projects. Would you like to give us a brief explanation on the ratings you proposed?

Repeat Step 6 to 8 until 8 construct poles have been elicited.

Step 9 - Rating of supplied construct. We have supplied a contrast of our own that asks the question of the value added by OGD in the citizen participation project. please rank the 9 projects on a scale of 1 to 7, 1 being closest to no added-value and 7 closest to the high added-value.

Step 10 - Summary and review. Let us take a moment to review the contrasts that you have written. Are you satisfied with them? Do you think that they accurately reflect your perceptions of the added-value of OGD in citizen participation projects? Do you have any final comment on the exercise?

Step 11 - Snowball sampling. Are there other people in your municipality or from other organizations that you believe would be interesting for us to interview as well?

Step 12 - Expression of gratitude. These were all the questions we wanted to discuss today. We would like to thank you for the time you dedicated to the interview.

Appendix 2 – Archetypes conceptualization and List of Project Examples

To conceptualize the archetypes, we reviewed extant literature following a hermeneutic approach (Boell and Cecez-Kecmanovic, 2014). Hermeneutic literature reviews involve iterative cycles of acquiring and analyzing/classifying literature to learn and build an understanding. This allowed us to acquire existing citizen participation project examples as well as analyze and classify them iteratively. To acquire literature, we used keywords such as “open data” or “open government data”, and “public” or “citizens”, and “participation”, or “participatory”, “transparency”, “engagement”, “co-creation”, “co-production” on online databases. We also relied on citations and a set of texts we already knew of. We used a core-categorization procedure (Jancowicz, 2005) to sort the projects mentioned in the articles into categories and continued iterating until no additional category emerged, meaning that we reached saturation in the understanding we were building. In addition, we made the decision to stop acquiring literature knowing that the categories conceptualized at this point (i.e., the archetypes), would be revised with dozens of elements elicited during the interviews.

Below are the 20 articles we collected throughout the hermeneutic review.

1. Böhm, C., Freitag, M., Heise, A., Lehmann, C., Mascher, A., Naumann, F., ... & Schmidt, M. (2012). GovWILD: integrating open government data for transparency. In Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on World Wide Web (pp. 321-324).
2. Cantador, I., Cortés-Cediel, M. E., & Fernández, M. (2020). Exploiting Open Data to analyze discussion and controversy in online citizen participation. *Information Processing & Management*, 57(5), 102301.
3. Coenen, J., Houben, M., & Vande Moere, A. (2019). Citizen dialogue kit: Public polling and data visualization displays for bottom-up citizen participation. In Companion Publication of the 2019 on Designing Interactive Systems Conference 2019 Companion (pp. 9-12).
4. Cordasco, G., De Donato, R., Malandrino, D., Palmieri, G., Petta, A., Pirozzi, D., ... & Vicidomini, L. (2017). Engaging citizens with a social platform for open data. In Proceedings of the 18th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research (pp. 242-249).
5. Craveiro, G. S., & Martano, A. M. (2014). Caring for My Neighborhood: a platform for public oversight. In Workshop on Agents, Virtual Societies and Analytics (pp. 117-126). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
6. Gagliardi, D., Schina, L., Sarcinella, M. L., Mangialardi, G., Niglia, F., & Corallo, A. (2017). Information and communication technologies and public participation: interactive maps and value added for citizens. *Government Information Quarterly*, 34(1), 153-166.
7. Gascó-Hernández, M., Martin, E. G., Reggi, L., Pyo, S., & Luna-Reyes, L. F. (2017). Citizen co-production through open data: cases of citizen training and engagement. In Proceedings of the 18th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research (pp. 562-563).
8. Hosio, S., Goncalves, J., Kostakos, V., & Riekkki, J. (2014). Exploring civic engagement on public displays. *User-centric technology design for nonprofit and civic engagements*, 91-111.
9. Hung, M. J., & Hsieh, W. H. (2019). Examining the Perception and Use of Open Crime Data from a Citizen Perspective. *Chinese Public Administration Review*, 10(1), 46-59.
10. Kalampokis, E., Hausenblas, M., & Tarabanis, K. (2011). Combining social and government open data for participatory decision-making. In Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Electronic Participation (pp. 36-47).
11. Kim, N. W., Jung, J., Ko, E. Y., Han, S., Lee, C. W., Kim, J., & Kim, J. (2016). Budgetmap: Engaging taxpayers in the issue-driven classification of a government budget. In Proceedings of the 19th ACM Conference on Computer-Supported Cooperative Work & Social Computing (pp. 1028-1039).
12. Lago, N., Durieux, M., Pouleur, J.-A., Scoubeau, C., Elsen, C., & Schelings, C. (2019). Citizen participation through digital platforms: the challenging question of data processing for cities. In Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Smart Cities, Systems, Devices and Technologies (pp. 19-25).

13. Meijer, A., & Potjer, S. (2018). Citizen-generated open data: An explorative analysis of 25 cases. *Government Information Quarterly*, 35(4), 613-621.
14. Noyman, A., Holtz, T., Kröger, J., Noennig, J. R., & Larson, K. (2017). Finding places: HCI platform for public participation in refugees' accommodation process. *Procedia computer science*, 112, 2463-2472.
15. Pak, B., Chua, A., & Vande Moere, A. (2017). FixMyStreet Brussels: socio-demographic inequality in crowdsourced civic participation. *Journal of Urban Technology*, 24(2), 65-87.
16. Puusaar, A., Johnson, I. G., Montague, K., James, P., & Wright, P. (2018). Making open data work for civic advocacy. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 2(CSCW), 1-20.
17. Schmuderer, S., Zink, R., & Gamerith, W. (2019). Citizen Participation via Digital Maps: A Comparison of Current Applications. In *GI Forum-Journal of Geographic Information Science* (Vol. 7, No. 2, pp. 34-46).
18. Sivarajah, U., Weerakkody, V., Waller, P., Lee, H., Irani, Z., Choi, Y., ... & Glikman, Y. (2016). The role of e-participation and open data in evidence-based policy decision making in local government. *Journal of Organizational Computing and Electronic Commerce*, 26(1-2), 64-79.
19. Sieber, R. E., & Johnson, P. A. (2015). Civic open data at a crossroads: Dominant models and current challenges. *Government Information Quarterly*, 32(3), 308-315.
20. Skouloudakis, A., & Christopoulou, E. (2021). Participatory budgeting: Combining smart cities and open data. In *Proceedings of the 25th Pan-Hellenic Conference on Informatics* (pp. 276-282).

Below are the 12 examples selected to be included in the list provided to interviewees.

Source	Archetype	Description
(Cantador et al., 2020)	4	A participatory budget allowing citizens to propose and debate project ideas. Statistics available in open data are used to see if there are correlations between the participation in a neighborhood and characteristics of the neighborhood. For example, correlation between the percentage of elderly citizens and the number of interactions on the platform.
(Puusaar et al., 2018)	1	Encourage bottom-up participation (i.e., on the citizens' initiative) about a range of issues by providing them with open data. The open data is processed and visualized so that it is usable by non-professionals.
(Schmuderer et al., 2019)	3	Citizens are invited to propose ideas on how to implement climate protection locally. They express their ideas using an interactive geographical map tool. Citizens are provided with documents explaining the concept of climate protection as well as publicly available maps of electric charging stations and the cycle path network, among others. Open data is used to create pdf documents made available to citizens for supporting the activity.
(Hosio et al., 2014)	3	A screen is installed in the city, on the site of a renovation project. The screen shows information on the renovation project and welcomes citizens to type any feedback they have on the project.
(Kalampokis et al., 2011)	4	The municipality is working on a draft law aiming to cut the police budget. Citizens, without being explicitly invited to do so, use social media to express what they think of this. The municipality is interested to know and collects the content and location information of the social media posts. Then, it can combine the location information with the open data available for this location (e.g., demographics and crime rate) to see if there is any relationship.
(Kim et al., 2016)	1	The municipality provides citizens with the list of budget programs available as open data that can be visualized in an interactive tool. Citizens can link each budget program to the social issues they think they are related to. This allows citizens to navigate the budget information by social issues.
(Böhm et al., 2012)	1	Linked open data is used to integrate spending open data from multiple sources. The data is made available to citizens through a visualization interface for transparency purposes.
(Pak et al., 2017)	6	Citizens are invited to use a mobile application to notify the city about urban incidents such as potholes.
(Coenen et al., 2019)	2	Several small screens are installed in different locations. They display a visual representation of open data such as the evolution of sport activity in the previous year and ask citizens to express themselves on the data they see by pressing a button.

(Noyman et al., 2017)	3	Citizens are invited to workshops aiming to propose location ideas for refugee accommodation. Geographic data on the city's smallest administrative units (parcels) was enriched by data such as general ownership or land use. Then, citizens discussed these places' suitability for refugee accommodation in an informed manner.
(Cordasco et al., 2017)	2	A tool making it possible to browse open data, create visualizations from the selected data, and create collectively open data sets. The tool also offers a discussion space in which citizens can group and discuss specific topics.
(Hung and Hsieh, 2019)	1	The municipality publishes online open data about crime. The objective is to encourage citizen participation in crime prevention by encouraging dialogue between informed citizens and police departments.

Appendix 3 – Grid Template

	Proj. 1	Proj. 2	Proj. 3	Proj. 4	Proj. 5	Proj. 6	Proj. 7	Proj. 8	Proj. 9	
Construct 1 Pole a	X	X					X			Construct 1 Pole b
Construct 2 Pole a		X	X					X		Construct 2 Pole b
Construct 3 Pole a	X		X		X					Construct 3 Pole b
Construct 4 Pole a				X	X		X			Construct 4 Pole b
Construct 5 Pole a					X	X		X		Construct 5 Pole b
Construct 6 Pole a		X		X		X				Construct 6 Pole b
Construct 7 Pole a			X	X					X	Construct 7 Pole b
Construct 8 Pole a		X			X				X	Construct 8 Pole b
OGD brings no added-value										OGD brings high added-value